

Flux/Flow Equations and Momentum as $p=Ev$ Versus $v=E/p$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 11, 2022

In previous notes we argued that two flow/flux equations d/dx (partial) $A(x,t)=p$ and d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ for free particles (where x/t is set to v after the derivatives are taken) may be used to describe classical mechanics, both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics (for a free particle with rest mass) and lead to the form of special relativity for a particle with rest mass. In this note we consider (as in (1)) the situation for a particle with no rest mass. We argue that the two flow/flux equations still pertain, but that there is a different equation for momentum (which as a function of $E(v)$ and v) is related to energy flow. For a particle with no rest mass, $v=E/p$ while for one with mass $p=E(v)/v$. How is this possible? We argue that $v=E/p$ describes an object with energy which is entirely active in creating motion i.e. energy flow. In other words for $pv=E$, $p \rightarrow 0$ and $v \rightarrow \infty$ means $E \rightarrow 0$ which does not allow for rest energy. This describes a classical wave and also the photon or phonon. Such an object cannot be at rest because its energy is equivalent to motion so to speak. It is possible to trap such a particle in a box so it bounces back and forth. In such a case, there is rest energy and a different notion of energy flow, namely $p=E(v)/v$. Thus, we argue that there is no contradiction in having two equations for momentum, one pertaining to particles with rest mass and the other to those without.

Flow/Flux Equations

We argue that two flow/flux equations applied to free particles represent the physics contained in free particle classical mechanics, relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics (for a particle with rest mass with the option of introducing spin) and also give the form of special relativity for a particle with rest mass. We further argue that these two flux/flow equations also hold for particles with no rest mass and that there is a link between the two cases. The flow/flux equations are:

$$d/dx \text{ (partial) } A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ (partial) } A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b))$$

These are general equations describing energy flow out of a cell dx in dt . $-E$ indicates energy is being lost in time, holding the position fixed. Nowhere does rest mass appear in ((1a)) and ((1b)). A general solution of ((1a)) and ((1b)) is given by:

$$A(x,t) = (-Et+px) \quad ((2))$$

If one wishes to create an eigenvalue equation, one may use $\exp(iA)$ as a solution i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

This is usually called a wave from classical wave mechanics, but one does not need to think in terms of physical waves. The solution describes energy flow/flux and applies both to waves such as phonons and photons which have no rest mass and to particles with rest mass.

In the case of a particle with rest mass one uses $p=E(v)/v$ which together with ((1a)) and ((1b)) lead to $A=tL(v)$, $p=dL/dv$ and $-E= L -pv$. Writing this as a differential equation in L and dL/dv and solving leads to $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$). It is an assumption, however, that $p=E(v)/v$ and this holds for particles with rest mass, not for ones without. A classical wave satisfies:

$dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ or $v= E/p$. Thus there are two very different definitions of momentum, namely:

$p=E(v)/v$ for particles with rest mass ((3a)) and
 $v= E/p$ ((4a)) for particles with no rest mass.

Both of these, however, satisfy ((1a)) and ((1b)) the flow/flux equations. The latter ((4a)) leads to a wave equation:

$$d/dt d/dt \exp(-iEt+ipx) = v^*v d/dx d/dx \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

The wave equation ((5)) follows from classical physics in a number of situations. First, there are waves on a string. Secondly, a wave equation follows from the combination of various conservation equations associated with Boltzmann's transport equation and leads to phonons and finally a wave equation follows from Maxwell's em equations and describes photons. All of these, however, seem to be linked to the two flow equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) which describes their underlying physics (although in a more general manner) than the usual classical approach which gives exact values for the velocity in terms of quantities in the classical equations.

Meaning of $v=E/p$

A classical wave (e.g. photons and phonons) satisfies $v=E/p$ and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is a solution of ((1a)) and ((1b)) with the added constraint $dA=0= -E dt + p dx$. One may see that $pv=E$ implies if $v \rightarrow 0$ then $p \rightarrow 0$ and $E \rightarrow 0$ so there is no "rest" energy. In other words the energy of the object is involved specifically in its motion. There is no energy without motion as in the photon or phonon case. For example, a photon in a vacuum must always be moving with speed c . A sound wave (in one direction) which does not move is not a sound wave. Thus energy and motion are almost synonymous. Such is not the case with an object with a rest mass, yet the flow equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) of the two are the same.

Object with a Rest Mass

An object with a rest mass has energy and momentum (energy flow), but if $v \rightarrow 0$ $p \rightarrow 0$, but E does not, unlike the phonon/photon case. Thus one cannot have $pv=E$ as the momentum equation. Consider $E(m_0,v)$ and imagine v is very small. P should be an odd function in v so one has:

$$p= E(m_0,v) (v+ a v^3 + \dots) \quad ((6))$$

To first order one has $p=E(m_0,v) v$ which is of the form of a flux equation. How may one link the two scenarios?

Linking $p=E(m_0,v) v$ and $vp=E$

It was argued that for a photon/phonon, the particle must always be in motion. In other words there is no sense of the particle being at rest. Its energy is actively moving it. As argued in (1), such a particle may be localized or trapped in a box. It still is continually moving, but now back and forth, as to create the sense of energy in a localized region, albeit one with some length. As a result, there is rest mass m_0 (so to speak) and one must change the notion of momentum p i.e. energy flow. One may note that in this scenario momentum of the box is artificial in that one considers a rest mass m_0 (which is not really a rest mass, but energy flow) and then moves the entire box. Thus one obtains a new momentum $p=E(v)v$ which is a “construct” to describe the scenario in place. Thus one does not have a contradiction in having two definitions for momentum i.e. $vp=E$ for a massless photon/phonon and $p=E(v)v$ for a particle with a rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that two general flow/flux equations d/dx (partial) $A(x,t) = p$ and d/dt (partial) $A(x,t) = -E$ describe both particles with rest mass and those without. The same solution $A=-Et+px$ or $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for an eigenvalue equation applies to both, but p is defined differently in each case which may at first be a surprise. Massless particles such as photons or phonons satisfy $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ or $pv=E$ which is equivalent to a wave equation $d/dt d/dt W = vv d/dx d/dx W$ for $W=\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Such wave equations follow from classical physics i.e. the equation for a wave in a string, a wave equation from conserved equations linked to Boltzmann's transport equations (phonons) and a wave equation from Maxwell's em equations (photons).

A particle with rest mass does not satisfy $pv=E$ because this equation implies that as $v \rightarrow 0$ and $p \rightarrow 0$ then $E \rightarrow 0$ and this cannot be as there is rest mass. A different equation is needed namely $p=E(v)v$. Using this, together with ((1a)) and ((1b)) one may derive the form of special relativity i.e. $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) which is equivalent to $EE=pp+m_0m_0$ and yields the Klein-Gordon equation if one uses the eigenvalue form of ((1a)) and ((1b)).

One may ask how it is physically possible to have two equations for momentum. We suggest that one may trap a massless particle in a box e.g. a photon and have it bounce back and forth. It is moving all of the time, but one may “pretend” that there is motionless energy i.e. rest energy localized within the box. In such a case, momentum or energy flow pertains to the entire box moving. This is a scenario (as really the photon in the box as viewed at each instant in time is not rest mass, but momentum), but seems to explain why one may have a different momentum energy velocity expression for a particle with rest mass i.e. $p=E(v)v$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity from Lagrangian Formalism Part II?(preprint, zenodo, 2022)

